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Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI): An Intervention Plan among Grade 9 Non-Readers

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Abstract

This descriptive pre-experimental quantitative study employing pre-test and post-test approach aimed to address low reading comprehension levels among the 33 identified non-readers in Grade 9 students at Asuncion National High School through the Comp-Reading Initiative. Statistical tools are used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. Pre-test and post-test results across four indicators showed significant improvements. Prior to the intervention, Positive Attitude Towards Reading had a mean score of 2.67 (Low) in the pre-test and 4.56 (Very High) in the post-test; Main Idea Identification and Question Answering improved from 2.52 (Low) to 4.37 (Very High); Vocabulary Understanding and Development rose from 2.90 (Moderate) to 4.55 (Very High); and Reading Fluency increased from 2.65 (Low) to 4.50 (Very High). These results indicate substantial enhancement in students' reading comprehension skills. Significant difference of the tests' scores shows the T-value of -20.949 and p-value of <.001 which indicates that the null hypothesis will be rejected, since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions with stakeholders provided further insights. Themes from the interviews included Pre-initiative Challenges, Varied Levels of Comprehension, and Identified Areas for Improvement regarding pre-intervention reading comprehension. Post-intervention, themes such as Improved Comprehension Skills, Evidence of Enhanced Reading Comprehension, and Overall Positive Shift in Comprehension Levels emerged. Stakeholder perspectives highlighted themes like Diverse Interventions, Intended Outcomes and Goals, and Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration, demonstrating comprehensive support for the intervention's effectiveness. Overall, the study underscores the success of the Comp-Reading Initiative in significantly improving Grade 9 students' reading comprehension levels.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, intervention plan, initiative, non-readers*

Introduction

In our education system and social lives, reading is crucial in any language. It forms the basis for writing, vocabulary acquisition, grammar improvement, and spelling. Those who struggle with reading, known as Non-readers may find any form of written content boring, inconsistent, or difficult to understand. They may have trouble grasping the main ideas, details, or making connections within a text, leading to decreased motivation and create a negative attitude towards reading. Non-readers often read infrequently and do not like to read, lacks effective word attacking skills, and has limited language and vocabulary (Chandran & Shah, 2019).

Consequently, this phenomenon occurs in the United Kingdom. According to Mulcahy et al. (2019), roughly 16% of adults in the United Kingdom are functionally illiterate, making the United Kingdom the illiteracy leader in the developed world. Many children and adults fall basic level of reading which they consider not unique since adult has 14 percentage of having 'below basic' reading ability and 21 percent of having reading ability below a reading age of 11. This is undeniable that some are struggling with understanding what they are reading and, they often mislay their aspiration to continue reading.

In the Philippines, according to numerous observations by the locals, there are still children who cannot comprehend the English language. Cabalo and Cabalo (2019) identified in a study that around 58.26 percent, or 187 out of 321 students, belong to the frustration level of reading, 30.22 percent, or 97 students, belong to the instructional level, and only 37, or 11.53 percent, were considered independent readers in the Southern District of Hilongo in Leyte. This is somehow caused by the challenges faced by the teachers when language learning and distance learning occur during the COVID-19 pandemic (Cagas, 2022).

In the Division of Davao del Norte, particularly in Asuncion National High School, it has been spotted that there have been Grade 9 students are struggling in comprehending what they have read, and has very limited language and vocabulary. The books and texts that they have read led them to confusion and misunderstanding which results to attain low scores during exams and quizzes. Moreover, short attention span is also evident in the students which led them to lose focus on what they have read. This skill, which is comprehending, is a vital skill that a student should attain for them to be able to cope with academic competence needed for higher years in studying.

This action research contributes to the broader social needs on addressing problems and issues regarding the reading aspect of the students. Additionally, this action research is timely and essential in addressing the existing prevalence of lack of reading comprehension as well as their attitudes in reading, vocabulary, and question answering. Consequently, this study holds significant social relevance as it addresses the evolving language needs of the students especially when it comes to reading comprehension. By yielding insightful results, it enriches our understanding of how to address this specific problem using diverse strategy and identify if the proposed intervention is effective or otherwise. This knowledge not only enhances our understanding about the levels of reading

comprehension among the students but also how to provide solutions on the diverse needs of the students not only on their comprehension but also on their vocabulary, attitudes in reading, and question answering.

Further, with the thorough search for relevant literature addressing reading comprehension, the researcher has found the study of Pellegrini et al. (2021) entitled “The Effectiveness of a Reading Comprehension Program for elementary school students: a quasi-experimental study”. Their focus is to provide an intervention named Reading Comprehension-Reciprocal Teaching (RC-RT) which was designed to evaluate the impact of the RC-RT intervention on reading comprehension and summarizing skills of fourth graders. Furthermore, the study of Balero & Maborang (2023) entitled “Exploring Factors Affecting Reading Comprehension Skills: A Quasi-Experimental Study on Academic Track Strands, Learning Modalities, and Gender” their focus is to examine the impact of academic track strands, learning modalities, and gender differences on reading comprehension.

However, when referred to the scope and locale of this study, the researcher has not come across researches on the descriptive-quantitative method focusing on one-group pretest posttest approach perspective in addressing students’ reading comprehension, their attitudes, vocabulary, and question answering employing CRI intervention. This means that there has no study that specifically focused on the one-group pretest posttest addressing the needs of non-readers such as reading comprehension, attitude in reading, vocabulary, and question answering. This therefore, established the research gap of the study.

Research Questions

The research questions below are to investigate the identified non-readers and formulate remediation on how to further develop their reading comprehension. The research questions that guided this study are the following:

1. What is the level of the reading comprehension among Grade 9 students before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention has been implemented based on:
 - 1.1. positive attitude towards reading;
 - 1.2. main idea identification and question answering;
 - 1.3. vocabulary understanding and development; and
 - 1.4. reading fluency?
2. What is the level of the reading comprehension among Grade 9 students after the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention has been implemented based on:
 - 2.1. positive attitude towards reading;
 - 2.2. main idea identification and question answering;
 - 2.3. vocabulary understanding and development; and
 - 2.4. reading fluency?
3. What is the significant difference between pre-test and post-test employing the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention?
4. What is the status of the reading comprehension among Grade 9 students before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention has been implemented?
5. What is the status of the reading comprehension among Grade 9 students after the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention has been implemented?
6. What insights can you share to the school administrators, teachers, and stakeholders with regards to action/intervention taken?

Proposed Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

The Comprehensive Readers Initiative (CRI) is a multifaceted intervention program designed to enhance reading comprehension skills among non-reader students. Non-readers are those students or individuals who lack the skills of a fluent reader. They read below the level of the grade they are in which makes them struggle with comprehension, attitude, and vocabulary. This initiative incorporates a blend of targeted instructional strategies, and collaborative activities to foster a deeper understanding of texts across various genres and subjects. It plays a crucial role in fostering a dynamic learning atmosphere, yielding advantages for both educators and learners. Students derive benefit from the additional support offered in grasping challenging concepts, fostering an enhancement in both comprehension and vocabulary enhancement.

The researchers developed an intervention called "Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI)" specifically designed to improve the reading comprehension skills of identified non-readers among the students from the chosen school. Upon implementation of the intervention, identified students will be having their session in weekdays every last period in the afternoon which is 3:30pm to 4:30pm from Monday to Thursday and one whole day class during Friday since it is their “Catch-up-Friday” that lasts in three (3) weeks, which is intentionally implemented to further address the needs of diverse students.

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher shall collaborate with the program head of the English department in Grade 9 to identify who among the students are qualified for the study. The program head of the grade 9 English department will choose students based on their acquired historical data. In identifying the participants, there are overall 10 sections in grade 9 level, and only 6 sections have these students who are qualified for the study. There will be a total of thirty-three (33) students in grade 9 which was identified by the program head as the respondents who are observed to be non-readers. Then, Pre-Test will be administered to identify their prior level

of reading comprehension. Afterwards, various strategies will be employed related to the goal such as passage reading, volunteer reading, and any activity involving reading, which is to improve the reading comprehension of the students along with the enhanced attitude towards reading, question answering, vocabulary enhancement, and reading fluency, which are part of the implementation. After the activities, a Post-Test will be administered to identify whether there will be an increase of level of reading comprehension among respondents. Then, a comparative analysis will then be conducted between the data obtained from the pre-test and the data obtained after the intervention is implemented.

Before commencing the action research, a thorough orientation will be conducted for participants, introducing the intervention along with a detailed explanation of the study's intentions and methodologies. Afterward, participants will be informed, ensuring that their identity will remain anonymous and with utmost discretion. Moreover, to safeguard the well-being of participants, the researchers will engage in a comprehensive discussion highlighting the benefits of various reading exercises. This discussion will serve as a guide, outlining the diverse activities participants will undertake during the intervention. The researchers are committed to ensuring that the instruments and strategies employed significantly contribute to the participants' development and enhancement of reading comprehension in every session conducted.

Weeks into incorporating the techniques and strategies of the CRI intervention, the researchers will arrange an interview involving 10 participants to actively contribute at every stage—development, planning, implementation, and evaluation, as well as five (5) teachers to attest the effectivity of the intervention proposed. This collaborative method empowers participants to take ownership of the initiative, transforming it into a collective and shared endeavor.

The primary objective of this study is to cultivate and improve the reading comprehension skills of the identified non-readers in grade 9 at Asuncion National High School. In the pursuit of this goal, the researchers will adhere to a set of guiding questions to structure and inform the study's direction.

Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) provides targeted support to address individual learning needs, helping students overcome challenges and gradually grasp simple to complex concepts. The personalized nature of the intervention allows for tailored instruction, fostering a deeper understanding of reading materials. Additionally, it enhances students' confidence in tackling diverse texts, ultimately contributing to improved overall comprehension skills. By focusing on specific areas of difficulty, CRI empowers students to navigate and comprehend various types of content, laying a foundation for academic success and lifelong learning.

After the implementation, the researchers are eager to witness the participants' progress and advancements in reading comprehension and vocabulary, as well as their attitude towards reading. The expectation is for a positive transformation in the academic development of the participants, envisioning heightened success in their educational journey. The researchers are optimistic that the invested efforts using the intervention will translate into a more successful and fulfilling academic experience for the participants, setting the stage for ongoing progress and achievement.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed quantitative research utilizing a pre-experimental descriptive one-group pretest posttest approach research design. According to Thyer (2012), one-group pretest posttest design is a group research design where a single group of participants is observed twice (pretest – posttest). Studies done in with special treatment or interventions are known as efficacy studies, and are used to demonstrate if a given treatment can produce positive results. It is a design and useful tool that helps to identify any changes in the indicators that occur before and after the introduction of the intervention or treatment.

This method is necessary in pursuing this action research wherein the aim is to assess how effective a strategy is by selecting and choosing the respondents to be tested using pre-test and post-test conducted by the researchers. The researchers will use the intervention namely “Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI)” which aims to address the needs of non-readers such as their reading comprehension level, attitude, vocabulary, reading fluency, and question answering. There will be a prior survey and after the implementation of intervention, a final survey will be conducted. The study is quantitative as it includes the numerical data of the identified respondents and the mean obtained from the data, which makes it suited for quantitative study.

Respondents

This study was conducted at Asuncion National High School, a secondary public school situated in Purok 12, Poblacion, Asuncion, Davao del Norte. In the selection of the participants, the head of the English department in Grade 9 identified the students that are qualified for the study. Cohen (2007) advised that a quantitative study to be conducted with heterogeneous group would comprise at least 14 participants. In this study the researchers will have thirty-three (33) Grade 9 students, with the help of the Head of English department and the teachers inside the school, students will be as respondents in the study. The participants are mainly from Asuncion National High School. Moreover, this study employed purposive sampling, a type of non-probability sampling, involves the deliberate selection of specific individuals based on their relevance to the research. This method is particularly useful when the researcher has specific knowledge about the population and can select a sample that is most representative of the population (Curtis, 2011).

<i>Grade</i>	<i>Number of Students</i>
Marcos	4
Osmeña	4
Garcia	4
Quirino	5
Aquino	6
Magsaysay	10
Total	33

Instruments

The study adapted the survey questionnaire on improving reading through the use of multiple intelligences by Albero et al. (2015). This questionnaire aims to assess the level of reading comprehension of the students as well as their attitude towards reading, question answering, vocabulary and their reading fluency. Then, questions are modified to suit for the goals of this study, which undergone validation by the panel of experts before utilization. Furthermore, before utilizing the survey questionnaire, it undergone validation from the research panels and was pilot tested to ensure validity and reliability of the results obtained from the survey questionnaire used.

Moreover, the researchers provided five-point Likert scale to measure and identify the status of reading comprehension of the students involved in the study. Upon utilization, the respondents will just put a check (✓) mark on the box appropriate on their level. The scale ranges from very high to very low, consisting range of means from 5.0 as the highest and 1.0 as the lowest. The following table will show the range of means, description and the corresponding interpretation of the scale provided.

Procedure

Mathison (1988) highlights the importance of using data collection procedures in a study to obtain reliable data from a variety of sources. In this study, the researchers utilized pre-and post- tests method in data collection. This study used a one-group pre-test-post-test design through an experimented reading comprehension levels of the participants when Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention is implemented. To identify the participants, the researchers collaborated with the program head of grade 9 English department which they will be the one to choose the appropriate participants of the study. After identifying, the researchers respectfully asked the respondents whether they would want to take part in the study or not. The researchers were not in any means deceive the participants knowing it is morally unacceptable. If they do not agree, the researchers expressed gratitude for giving an honest reply and apologies for consuming their time. The researchers were also revealed their faces to the respondents to show their sincerity in choosing and conducting the study. Then, the researchers conducted a pretest. During the pre-test stage, assessment sheet was disseminated to the respondents of the study in order to know about their prior level of reading comprehension of the English language in the context of study. The study conducted a pre-test prior to intervention to determine the level of reading comprehension of the participants who are non-readers. After which, the intervention will be implemented for a total of 3 weeks, 1 hours per session every Monday to Thursday and 8 hours every Friday, a total of 36 hours, and post-test will be conducted after completing the sessions.

Before the conduct of the study, researchers collaborated with the head of English Teacher in grade 9 who is presently in the Asuncion National High School. The researchers also asked permission from the school principal and Grade 9 class advisers to conduct the study and inform them of the schedule and duration of the intervention. In addition, the reading materials that is used in the pre-test will be the adapted and modified test which undergone checking and validation from the Grade 9 English Coordinator. upon having the pre-test, students are placed in a quiet room to ensure they are not distracted when answering. After the conduct of the pre-test, the researchers collected the responses and analyzed the scores to obtain mean scores per indicators given. Afterwards, the CRI intervention was then utilized to develop the students' reading comprehension through various activities and materials relating to reading such as books for oral reading, storytelling, question answering, and other reading assessments. The implementation of the said intervention lasted for three (3) weeks. After the application of the intervention, post-test was conducted using the same test kit as the pre-test to determine if there will be improvement on the reading comprehension among the participants after the intervention. Furthermore, the process of collecting data is to know if there is a significant improvement on the reading comprehension among non-readers before and after the intervention is implemented.

Data Analysis

Statistical tools are a set of techniques used to analyze data and draw inferences about the population being studied. It involves organizing data, summarizing key patterns, and calculating the probability that observations could have occurred randomly. In Statistics, data collection is a process of gathering information from all the relevant sources to find a solution to the research problem. It helps to evaluate the outcome of the problem. The data collection methods allow a person to conclude an answer to the relevant question (Buckley et al., 1976).

This study made use of the one group pretest-posttest design as it is the most suitable statistical tool to indicate whether there was a difference between the pre-test and post-test results after an intervention was done. The researchers then computed the mean of the data obtained and compared the means of both tests – pretest and posttest to determine the significant differences of the two tests, whether

it shows increase and decrease of the mean before and after the intervention was implemented.

Furthermore, the mean will be utilized to describe the students' response in initial and final results. It represents the average value of a set of data and is calculated by summing up all the values in the data set and then dividing that sum by the total number of values. Also, using paired T-test to determine if a sample is greater or less than a certain range of values, the T-test is frequently used to identify critical points of a distribution area. This is also used as evidence for both accepting and rejecting the null hypothesis. This can be also utilized in other statistical analyses that compare two sets of values.

Moreover, the researchers provided questions in the interview guide and have thematic analysis to identify the emerging themes that emerged from the response of the students as well as the teachers of the sections where students as respondents came from. Thematic analysis (TA) is concerned with the identification and analysis of patterns of meaning (themes) and constitutes a widely applicable and flexible tool involving translated responses of the participants involved (Braun and Clarke, 2013). It was done by clustering responses which shared the same thought and idea then was categorized based on the shared emerging theme with an assigned code and assigned theme. To check the credibility of the theme, the assigned themes from the thematic analysis was checked and further validated by panel of experts.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of the findings of the study. The data are presented in both tabular and textual forms. The findings relate to the research questions that guided the study.

Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Based on Positive Attitude Towards Reading

The Table 1.1 presents the pre-test data obtained from this indicator among Grade 9 students revealed that their attitude towards reading is rarely manifested which happens very infrequently and ranges into 1.90 to 2.60 and accumulate a total mean score of 2.67 which is described as Low.

Table 1.1. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students Before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented*

<i>Positive Attitude Towards Reading</i>		<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
1.	I enjoy spending my free time reading.	2.85	Moderate
2.	I find reading to be a relaxing activity.	2.64	Low
3.	I get excited about book recommendations from friends or teachers.	2.73	Moderate
4.	I look forward to learning new things through reading.	2.55	Low
5.	I prefer reading to other activities like watching TV or playing video games.	2.73	Moderate
Overall Mean		2.67	Low

From the pre-test result, the item 4 "I look forward to learning new things through reading." obtained the lowest mean score of 2.55 which is described as Low. Followed by item 2 "I find reading to be a relaxing activity." obtained a mean score of 2.64 which is described as Low. The item 3 "I get excited about book recommendations from friends or teachers." And item 5 "I prefer reading to other activities like watching TV or playing video games." obtained a same mean score of 2.73 which is described as Moderate. Lastly, the item 1 "I enjoy spending my free time reading." obtained the highest score among all items of 2.85 which is described as Moderate.

Table 1.2. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students After the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented*

<i>Positive Attitude Towards Reading</i>		<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
1.	I enjoy spending my free time reading.	4.79	Very High
2.	I find reading to be a relaxing activity.	4.52	Very High
3.	I get excited about book recommendations from friends or teachers.	4.42	Very High
4.	I look forward to learning new things through reading.	4.48	Very High
5.	I prefer reading to other activities like watching TV or playing video games.	4.61	Very High
Overall Mean		4.56	Very High

On the other hand, Table 1.2 presents the post-test data obtained from this indicator among Grade 9 students revealed that their attitude towards reading has increased after the application of the intervention and is always manifested without fail and ranges into 4.30 to 5.00 and obtained a total mean score of 4.56 which is described as Very High.

From the post-test results and the same indicator, the item 3 "I get excited about book recommendations from friends or teachers." obtained the lowest mean score of 4.42 which is described as Very High or it is always manifested without fail. Followed by item 4 "I look forward to learning new things through reading." that obtained the mean score of 4.48 and is described as Very High. The item 2 "I find reading to be a relaxing activity." obtained a mean score of 4.52 which is described as Very High. Moreover, item 5 "I prefer reading to other activities like watching TV or playing video games." obtained a mean score of 4.61 and is described as Very High. Lastly, the item 1 "I enjoy spending my free time reading." obtained the highest mean score of 4.79 which is described as Very High.

Overall, the total improvement of the attitude of the students towards reading increased from 2.67 which was described as Moderate to

4.56 which was described as Very High. This manifests that the intervention made by the researchers was implemented successfully with a positive result from the pre-test until the post-test. The gains present the attitude of the students towards reading which is remarkably positive since it showcases an increase of the interests when it comes to reading and comprehending the texts given to them.

According to the study focusing on engagement and motivation in reading, having a positive attitude towards reading is important as a critical factor in enhancing reading comprehension among students. The study suggests that students who are motivated and have a positive outlook towards reading are more likely to engage deeply with texts, which enhances their comprehension. They also demonstrate that a positive attitude towards reading not only increases the time students spend reading but also enhances the quality of their reading experience, significantly boosting reading comprehension levels (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2015).

In addition, according to the Children's Attitudes Toward Reading: A National Survey, underscores that a positive attitude towards reading significantly enhances reading comprehension. By promoting positive reading experiences and attitudes, educators can help students build strong reading skills, improve academic performance, and develop a lifelong love for reading (McKenna et al., 2018).

Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Based on Main Idea Identification and Question Answering

The pre-test result derived from Table 2.1 shows the level of the Grade 9 students before the application of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) intervention which also focuses on main idea identification and question answering for reading comprehension of the respondents.

Table 2.1. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students Before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented Based on Main Idea Identification and Question Answering*

<i>Main Idea Identification and Question Answering</i>		<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
1.	I can easily identify the main idea of a text after reading it.	2.70	Moderate
2.	I can answer questions about a text without having to look back at it frequently.	2.45	Low
3.	After reading, I can summarize the text in my own words.	2.42	Low
4.	I find it easy to discuss the content of what I've read with others.	2.45	Low
5.	I feel confident in my ability to locate specific information within a text when asked.	2.55	Low
Overall Mean		2.52	Low

From the pre-test result, it shows that there is a low range of mean score as 2.52 which is described as Low or it is rarely manifested which happens very infrequently. Based on the result on the 3rd item which obtained the lowest mean of the items – “After reading, I can summarize the text in my own words.”, it obtained a Low description which illustrates that the students before the intervention have low ability of summarizing the texts they have read. Followed by item 2 “I can answer questions about a text without having to look back at it frequently.” and item 4 “I find it easy to discuss the content of what I've read with others.” which both obtained a mean score of 2.45 and is described as Low. Moreover, the item “I feel confident in my ability to locate specific information within a text when asked.” obtained a mean score of 2.55 which is described as Low. Lastly, the item 1 “I can easily identify the main idea of a text after reading it.” which is the highest mean score among the items obtained 2.70 which is described as Moderate.

Table 2.2. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students After the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented Based on Main Idea Identification and Question Answering*

<i>Main Idea Identification and Question Answering</i>		<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
1.	I can easily identify the main idea of a text after reading it.	4.58	Very High
2.	I can answer questions about a text without having to look back at it frequently.	4.15	High
3.	After reading, I can summarize the text in my own words.	4.24	High
4.	I find it easy to discuss the content of what I've read with others.	4.27	High
5.	I feel confident in my ability to locate specific information within a text when asked.	4.64	Very High
Overall Mean		4.37	Very High

On the other hand, from the Table 2.2 illustrating the post-test results, progress and development is observed when it comes to mean scores since it illustrates increase. The item 5 “I feel confident in my ability to locate specific information within a text when asked.” obtained the highest mean score 4.64 which is described as Very High after having the intervention which shows that the students developed their comprehension by responding appropriately based on the texts read. Followed by item 1 “I can easily identify the main idea of a text after reading it.” which obtained a mean score of 4.58 and described as Very High. Followed by item 4 “I find it easy to discuss the content of what I've read with others.” obtained a mean score 4.27 which is described as High. Additionally, the item 3 “After reading, I can summarize the text in my own words.” obtained the mean score 4.24 which is described as High. Lastly, the item 2 “I can answer questions about a text without having to look back at it frequently.” obtained the lowest mean score 4.15 which is described as High or reading comprehension is oftentimes manifested which happens occasionally. Overall, the total mean score after the implementation of the intervention was done obtained 4.37 which is described as Always. This means that the intervention was effective since it illustrates mean difference of 1.85 as gain.

According to the Verbal Protocols of Reading (Afflerback, 1995), it highlighted the critical role of identifying the main idea and question answering in enhancing the reading comprehension among students which include active engagement, cognitive strategies,

text interaction, and critical thinking in which these strategies engage students actively with the text, improve their critical thinking and retention, and promote a more interactive and self-regulated reading experience (Pressley, 2019).

On the other hand, according to the Elements of Fostering and Teaching- Reading Comprehension, it was argued by prominent individuals that teaching students how to identify main ideas and answers questions is essential for enhancing reading comprehension. There are significant strategies that will be used which could promote focused reading, information integration, and effective comprehension monitoring that will lead to improve retention and application of knowledge across various contexts (Duke et al., 2015).

Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Based on Vocabulary Understanding and Development

The table 3.1 below shows the pre-test mean scores of the items provided pertaining to the level of the students' reading comprehension based on their vocabulary understanding as well as their prior skills before the intervention was applied.

Table 3.1. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students Before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented Based on Vocabulary Understanding and Development*

<i>Vocabulary Understanding and Development</i>		<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
1.	I often encounter new words while reading.	3.03	Moderate
2.	I look up the meanings of words I don't know to better understand the text.	2.73	Moderate
3.	I try to use new words that I learn in my daily conversations.	2.94	Moderate
4.	Understanding the meaning of words helps me grasp the overall message of the text.	3.00	Moderate
5.	I feel that my vocabulary is growing as I read more.	2.79	Moderate
Overall Mean		2.90	Moderate

From the pre-test, it illustrates the prior level of the students when it comes to vocabulary understanding and development and obtained an overall mean score 2.90 which was described as Moderate or reading comprehension is sometimes manifested which occurs infrequently. The item 1 "I often encounter new words while reading." which was the highest obtained a mean score of 3.03 and is described as Moderate. Followed by item 4 "Understanding the meaning of words helps me grasp the overall message of the text." obtained a mean score of 3.0 which is described as Moderate. Additionally, the item 3 "I try to use new words that I learn in my daily conversations." obtained a mean score of 2.94 which was described as Moderate. Followed by the item 5 "I feel that my vocabulary is growing as I read more." which obtained a mean score of 2.79 and described as Moderate. Lastly, the item 2 "I look up the meanings of words I don't know to better understand the text." obtained a mean score of 2.73 which is the lowest and is described as Moderate.

Table 3.2. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students After the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented Based on Vocabulary Understanding and Development*

<i>Vocabulary Understanding and Development</i>		<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
1.	I often encounter new words while reading.	4.79	Very High
2.	I look up the meanings of words I don't know to better understand the text.	4.30	Very High
3.	I try to use new words that I learn in my daily conversations.	4.61	Very High
4.	Understanding the meaning of words helps me grasp the overall message of the text.	4.52	Very High
5.	I feel that my vocabulary is growing as I read more.	4.55	Very High
Overall Mean		4.55	Very High

Furthermore, the result of the data obtained from the Table 3.2 illustrates significant difference after the intervention was implemented. From the item 1 "I often encounter new words while reading." which obtained the highest mean score of 4.79 which is described as Very High, it shows that new words encountered is always manifested or occurs without fail. Followed by the item 3 "I try to use new words that I learn in my daily conversations." which obtained a mean score 4.61 and described as Very High. Then, the item 5 "I feel that my vocabulary is growing as I read more." obtained a mean score of 4.55 which is described as Very High. The item 4 "Understanding the meaning of words helps me grasp the overall message of the text." obtained a mean score of 4.52 which is described as Very High. Lastly, the item 2 "I look up the meanings of words I don't know to better understand the text." which was the item obtained lowest mean score of 4.30 and is described as Very High. Overall, the total mean after the intervention was implemented was 4.55 which illustrates that vocabulary understanding and development is always manifested without fail.

According to the book of Beck and McKweon (2015) entitled "Bringing words to life: Robust Vocabulary Instruction" they argue that a deep and rich vocabulary is essential for comprehending complex texts across different subject areas. The approach to vocabulary instruction focuses on teaching words in rich contexts, fostering word connections, and providing multiple exposures to words in varied contexts. In addition, evidence-based strategies and activities were provided that educators can use to enhance students' vocabulary knowledge, which in turn supports their overall reading comprehension abilities.

On the other hand, another study also discussed the significance of both breadth and depth of vocabulary knowledge in reading comprehension. It was suggested that a robust vocabulary allows readers to comprehend text more effectively by enabling them to recognize and understand a wider range of words and their nuances. Aside from vocabulary expansion, the study also provides insights how educators can facilitate vocabulary acquisition through explicit instruction and meaningful encounters with words in context, thereby enhancing students' ability to comprehend what they read (Nagy & Herman, 2017).

Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Based on Reading Fluency

The Table 4.1 illustrates the significant difference of the level of reading comprehension of the students that is based on reading fluency before the implementation of the intervention CRI and the corresponding mean scores of every item provided.

Table 4.1. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students Before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented Based on Reading Fluency*

	Reading Fluency	Pre-Test	Descriptions
1.	I can read aloud smoothly and with expression.	2.52	Low
2.	I understand most of what I read on the first attempt.	2.42	Low
3.	I can maintain my focus while reading long texts without getting distracted.	2.67	Low
4.	My reading speed is adequate for completing my school or work tasks on time.	2.70	Moderate
5.	I can adjust my reading speed based on the difficulty of the text.	2.94	Moderate
	Overall Mean	2.65	Low

In the pre-test or before the intervention was implemented, the result of the data obtained was showing a mean score of 2.65 which is described as Low or the reading comprehension in terms of reading fluency of the students is rarely manifested which happens very infrequently. The item 5 "I can adjust my reading speed based on the difficulty of the text." got the highest mean score of 2.94 which is described as Moderate. Followed by item 4 "My reading speed is adequate for completing my school or work tasks on time." obtained a mean score of 2.94 which is described as Moderate. Then, the item 3 "I can maintain my focus while reading long texts without getting distracted." which obtained a mean score of 2.67 and is described as Low. The item 1 "I can read aloud smoothly and with expression." which obtained a mean score of 2.52 and is described as Low. Lastly, the item 2 "I understand most of what I read on the first attempt." which obtained the lowest mean score of 2.42 which is described as Low.

Table 4.2. *Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Among Grade 9 Students After the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention was Implemented Based on Reading Fluency*

	Reading Fluency	Post-Test	Descriptions
1.	I can read aloud smoothly and with expression.	4.30	Very High
2.	I understand most of what I read on the first attempt.	4.39	Very High
3.	I can maintain my focus while reading long texts without getting distracted.	4.48	Very High
4.	My reading speed is adequate for completing my school or work tasks on time.	4.64	Very High
5.	I can adjust my reading speed based on the difficulty of the text.	4.67	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.50	Very High

After the implementation, post-test was administered and the result of the data obtained illustrates that there are significant changes on the level of the reading comprehension and the reading fluency of the students after the intervention. From the item 5 "I can adjust my reading speed based on the difficulty of the text." which obtained the highest mean score of 4.67 and is described as Very High. Followed by item 4 "My reading speed is adequate for completing my school or work tasks on time." which obtained the mean score 4.64 which described as Very High. Then, the item 3 "I can maintain my focus while reading long texts without getting distracted." obtained a mean score of 4.48 which is described as Very High. The item 2 "I understand most of what I read on the first attempt." obtained a mean score of 4.39 which is described as Very High. Lastly, the item 1 "I can read aloud smoothly and with expression." which obtained the lowest mean score of 4.30 and is described as Very High.

Overall, the result illustrates that there are significant changes between the pre-test and the post-test data of the respondents garnering a difference of 1.85 which shows an increase of reading fluency of the students. This positive outcome underscores the importance of reading fluency in reading comprehension and idea generation of the students after the intervention has been implemented.

According to the report of the National Panel on the Assessment of the Scientific Research Literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction, it highlights one of the findings in the report is the importance of reading fluency in improving comprehension. In here, fluency defines as the ability to read accurately, smoothly, and with expression, is identified as a crucial component that supports comprehension by freeing resources for understanding the meaning of text rather than individual words (Fuchs et al., 2016).

In addition, according to an article entitled "Reading fluency" published in Reading Teacher, it emphasizes that reading fluency is not just a technical skill but a crucial component of effective reading comprehension. Thus, promoting fluency through appropriate instructional methods and encouraging practice, educators can significantly enhance students' ability to understand and interpret text across various subject areas (Rasinski, 2020).

Table 5. *Summary on the Level of Students' Reading Comprehension*

Factors of Reading Comprehension	Pre-Test	Descriptions	Post-Test	Descriptions
Positive Attitude Towards Reading	2.70	Moderate	4.56	Very High
Main Idea Identification and Question Answering	2.52	Low	4.38	Very High
Vocabulary Understanding and Development	2.90	Moderate	4.55	Very High

Reading Fluency	2.65	Low	4.50	Very High
Overall Mean	2.69	Moderate	4.50	Very High

Table 5 illustrates the summary of the results based on the data obtained before and after the implementation of the intervention Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) based on the average of the mean scores of the items on each indicator. As presented in the table, the Positive Attitude Towards Reading of the Grade 9 students increased from the mean score 2.70 to 4.56 which is described as Moderate to Very High and shows that the intervention helped them obtain positive attitude towards reading. Moreover, in Main Idea Identification and Question Answering shows changes from the mean score 2.52 to 4.38 which is described as Low to Very High. In Vocabulary Understanding and Development, it also illustrates development wherein from the mean score 2.90 it changes into 4.55 which is described as Moderate to Very High. Lastly, the Reading Fluency of the Grade 9 students based on the result before and after the implementation of the intervention was significantly changed from the mean score 2.65 to 4.50 which is described as Moderate to Very High. Overall, the application of the intervention which focuses on the reading comprehension of the students results as successful wherein there is a difference of the factors presented from pre-test to post-test and is illustrated by the overall mean score of 2.69 to 4.50 which is described as Moderate to Very High.

The Significant Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Employing the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention

Table 6 illustrates the significant difference of the pre-test and post-test of the intervention upon the implementation of it to the Grade 9 students which are the respondents of this study.

Table 6. Significant Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test

Type of Test	N	df	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Decision $\alpha=0.05$
Pre-Test	33		2.70	0.078	-20.949	< .001	Significant
Post-Test	33	32	4.49	0.048			

The overall result illustrates that the level of the reading comprehension of the Grade 9 students during the pre-test having a total mean of 2.70 which is described as Moderate and obtained a standard deviation of 0.078. On the other hand, from the post-test, it accumulates a total mean of 4.49 which is described as Very High and obtained a standard deviation of 0.048.

Moreover, based on the result of the significant difference of the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents from Grade 9 which undergone the intervention, the T-value of -20.949 and p-value of <.001 indicates that the null hypothesis of this study will be rejected, since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the intervention is found effective since and result illustrates that the actions taken is significant and implies that the hypothesis will be rejected.

The Status of The Reading Comprehension Among the Grade 9 Students Before the Comp-Reading Initiative Intervention Has Been Implemented

In-depth interviews and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants and participants. Several sub-questions are asked to elicit their concept regarding the status of the reading comprehension level among grade-9 students in Asuncion National High School. The major themes and sample statements for research question number 1 were presented in Table 1. Participants had their responses to their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, there are three major themes have emerged: (1) Pre-Initiative Reading Comprehension Challenges; (2) Varied Levels of Comprehension and Collective Struggle; and (3) Identified Areas for Improvement.

The result of this study found out that there are numerous difficulties that the students had to overcome. They had encountered pre-initiative reading comprehension challenges, one of the participants stated that the students in grade 9 had different levels of understanding prior to the comp-reading initiative. Some students engaged deeply with texts and showed strong comprehension skills, while others found it difficult to understand important ideas or deduce meanings. Based on the results of the study, it was showed that the students must overcome the obstacles before they can read on their own and comprehend text in an efficient manner. Given their potential to affect a child's overall learning trajectory and academic success, these issues must be addressed (K12 Reader, 2018). It was also revealed during the conduct of in-depth discussion that the students cope with the difficulties they experienced. It highlighted the tolerance while dealing with the behavior of the students in reading, as a matter of fact they varied levels of comprehension and collective struggle. The participants stated that the overall level of reading comprehension among grade 9 students varied. While some students demonstrated proficiency in understanding texts, others struggled to comprehend material at their grade level. There were instances where students could summarize texts accurately but had difficulty analyzing deeper themes or drawing inferences. As a result, it draws attention to the differences in students' reading comprehension skills and the collaborative efforts needed to close these gaps.

Table 7. Themes and Sample Statements on the Reading Comprehension among Grade-9 Students Before the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention has been implemented

Emerging Themes	Sample Statements
	Before the comp-reading initiative, I think many of us struggled to fully understand what we read. Sometimes, the

Pre-Initiative Reading Comprehension Challenges	<p>texts were too complex, and we couldn't grasp all the ideas. Other times, we might have rushed through the reading without really absorbing the information (IDI-01)</p> <p>Before the comp-reading initiative, the understanding of grade 9 students varied. While some students demonstrated strong comprehension skills and engaged deeply with texts, others struggled to grasp key concepts or infer meanings. Overall, there was room for improvement in their ability to comprehend texts across different subjects and genres (IDI-05)</p> <p>Uh, I guess before the comp-reading thing, grade 9 students didn't really understand what they read that much. Like, it was kind of tough for them, you know? Like, they probably didn't get all the stuff in the books or like, the main points and stuff. It was probably pretty tricky for them (FGD-02)</p> <p>Sometimes instead of understanding the real meaning of what we are reading we just makeup some ideas even though we are not sure if it is connected to the main idea of what we are reading. We do this to escape the frustration and get over with it (FGD-05)</p>
Varied Levels of Comprehension and Collective Struggle	<p>The overall level of reading comprehension among grade 9 students varied. While some students demonstrated proficiency in understanding texts, others struggled to comprehend material at their grade level. There were instances where students could summarize texts accurately but had difficulty analyzing deeper themes or drawing inferences (FGD-02)</p> <p>I'd say the overall level varied among students. Some were better at it than others, but as a class, I think we struggled collectively. It seemed like we needed more guidance and support to improve our reading comprehension skills (IDI-10)</p> <p>I think it's different for every student. Sometimes there are students who have a very low level of reading comprehension and some just need a little help and they will eventually improve (FGD-01)</p> <p>We have different level but all of us need time and all the help we need to help us improve. In the scale of 1-10 I could rate our level in 5 because the majority of the low level is higher than those who only need a little help (IDI-09)</p>
Identified Areas for Improvement	<p>Overall, I think we did our best, but there were definite areas where we could have done better. Some texts were easier for us to understand, while others posed more challenges. We often had discussions about what we read, but there were times when we struggled to articulate our thoughts because we didn't fully grasp the material (IDI-07)</p> <p>Grade 9 students demonstrated varying levels of performance in understanding texts before the comp-reading initiative. While some students excelled and demonstrated strong analytical skills, others struggled to comprehend material at their grade level. Overall, there was a need for targeted instruction and support to enhance students' reading comprehension abilities (FGD-03)</p> <p>How to chunk ideas and other reading strategies are what I think they need to improve their reading comprehension. There are different strategies and we need to know what is the type of method suited for them (FGD-05)</p> <p>To help us improve students like us who struggles in understanding the text we are reading need time and attention. With the help and guidance of our teachers they can give suggestions on what are the things we must improve (IDI-10)</p>

This result supports the claim of RV Caraig (2022), who claimed that the students display a range of comprehension skills in any educational setting because of variations in their cognitive development, prior knowledge, language ability, and resource availability. Despite of the difficulties of students found in the result, they must comprehend the common behavioral traits in order to ascertain their unique personalities and in order to achieve this, therefore, they have to identified areas for improvement and as what one of the participants said that Grade 9 students demonstrated varying levels of performance in understanding texts before the comp-reading initiative. While some students excelled and demonstrated strong analytical skills, others struggled to comprehend material at their grade level.

Overall, there was a need for targeted instruction and support to enhance students' reading comprehension abilities. As a result, it should focus on pinpointing specific aspects of reading education and comprehension that require enhancement to optimize student outcomes. By identifying these areas, educators and policymakers can implement targeted strategies to address weaknesses and foster better literacy development (Birt, 2020).

The Status of The Reading Comprehension Among the Grade 9 Students After the Comp-Reading Initiative Intervention Has Been Implemented

The major themes and sample statements for research question number 2 were presented in Table 2. Participants had their responses to their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, there are three major themes have emerged: (1) Post-Initiative Reading Improvement in Comprehension Skills; (2) Evidence of Enhanced Reading Comprehension; and (3) Overall Positive Shift in Comprehension Level.

The result of this study found out that there is an improvement in the students reading comprehension because of the strategies and techniques used while implementing the initiative. In the post-Initiative reading improvement in comprehension skills, one of the participants stated that grade 9 students shown significant improvement in understanding what they are reading after the comp-reading initiative. By the help of the implementations of the strategies and implementation students become more skillful in decoding text, identifying context of the text and making connection between different parts of the text. This is supported by Banditvilai (2020),

proving that reading strategies have a great impact on the students' reading comprehension ability. Students needed training or guidance on various reading strategies to understand how to apply them effectively for comprehending academic materials successfully.

Table 8. *Themes and Sample Statements on the Reading Comprehension Among Grade-9 Students After the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) Intervention has been implemented*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Post-Initiative Reading Improvement in Comprehension Skills	<p>I think we have shown improvement in understanding what we read after the comp-reading initiative. The initiative introduced new strategies and techniques that have helped us break down complex texts and grasp key concepts more effectively (IDI-01)</p> <p>I am confident to say that there is a significant improvement in understanding what we read after the comp-reading initiative. With the implementation of targeted strategies and interventions, I think we have become more proficient in decoding texts, identifying main ideas, and making connections between different parts of the text. (IDI-04)</p> <p>The recent implementation of interactive reading circles for grade 9 students has yielded noticeable improvements in their comprehension skills. By encouraging group discussions and employing innovative reading strategies, such as reciprocal teaching and peer-led analysis, students have been able to tackle challenging texts with greater confidence. As a result, students are not only comprehending texts more effectively but also developing valuable communication and analytical abilities that will serve them well beyond the classroom (FGD-02)</p> <p>Following the launch of the comp-reading initiative, grade 9 students have experienced a notable uptick in their reading comprehension abilities. Through personalized support and tailored interventions, students have honed their skills in deciphering texts, extracting key concepts, and drawing meaningful links between various passages. By employing methods such as scaffolded reading exercises and close reading techniques, educators have empowered students to engage more deeply with the material and extract nuanced insights. As a result, students not only demonstrate improved comprehension but also exhibit a heightened sense of literary analysis and critical thinking (FGD-04)</p>
Evidence of Enhanced Reading Comprehension	<p>Yes, there has been a noticeable improvement in our reading comprehension skill after the comp-reading initiative. Through the use of explicit instruction, scaffolded support, and regular practice, we have demonstrated enhanced skills in comprehension, inference-making, and critical analysis of texts (IDI-05)</p> <p>Yes, I believe there has been a noticeable improvement among grade 9 reading comprehension skills. They are better able to identify main ideas, make connections between different parts of the text, and infer meanings from context. Overall, the initiative has contributed to their growth as readers (FGD-04)</p> <p>The positive impact of the comp-reading initiative on grade 9 students' reading comprehension is unmistakable. By employing a multi-faceted approach encompassing direct instruction, gradual support, and consistent practice, students have exhibited marked progress in their ability to understand, infer, and critically evaluate texts. The initiative's emphasis on breaking down complex concepts into manageable chunks, coupled with opportunities for guided exploration and reflection, has empowered students to navigate challenging materials with greater ease and confidence. As a result, not only have their comprehension skills improved, but they have also developed a deeper appreciation for the intricacies of written communication (FGD-05)</p> <p>Without a doubt, our reading comprehension skills have taken a leap forward. We're now adept at spotting the core themes, linking various sections of the text, and deducing meanings from the surrounding context. This initiative has truly been a game-changer for us as readers. It's not just about understanding the words anymore; it's about delving deeper into the message and unraveling the layers of meaning hidden within. As a result, we've become more confident and discerning readers, equipped with the tools to navigate complex texts and extract valuable insights. It's been an enriching journey of growth and discovery (IDI-08)</p>
Overall Positive Shift in Comprehension Level	<p>The overall level of reading comprehension among grade 9 students has definitely improved after the comp-reading initiative. While there are still areas where we can continue to develop our skills, such as analyzing complex texts or interpreting symbolism, we have made significant progress overall (IDI-06)</p> <p>The overall level of reading comprehension among grade 9 students after the comp-reading initiative has seen a positive shift. While individual student progress may vary, there is a general trend of improved comprehension skills across the class. Students are better equipped to engage with a variety of texts and extract meaning from them effectively (IDI-03)</p> <p>The comp-reading initiative has undeniably led to a noticeable enhancement in the general reading comprehension of Grade-9 students. Although there remain aspects where further skill refinement is warranted, such as the analysis of intricate texts and the interpretation of symbolism, our collective advancement has been substantial (FGD-04)</p> <p>Following the implementation of the comp-reading initiative, there has been a favorable change observed in the overall reading comprehension of grade 9 students. Although the progress of each student may differ, there is a noticeable improvement in comprehension skills throughout the class. Students now possess enhanced abilities to interact with diverse texts and derive meaning from them proficiently (FGD-01)</p>

The result also revealed the evidence of enhanced reading comprehension of the students after the implementation of the comp-reading initiative. The participants all stated that there is a noticeable improvement in their reading comprehension. One participant also stated they also able to spot core themes, linking various sections of the text, and deducing meanings from the surrounding context. Following the implementation and data analysis from the instruments, participants felt that the strategies and techniques used had enhanced their

reading skills and positively shifted their attitudes. Reading became an enjoyable activity as they found the implemented strategies beneficial. Additionally, students could make predictions before reading, formulate questions to understand the author's intent, and summarize ideas after reading.

Consequently, these findings showed that using comprehension strategies effectively instilled a sense of accomplishment in the students and fostered a more positive attitude towards reading (Cárdenas 2020). The result also shows the overall positive shift in comprehension level. A participant stated that there is a noticeable improvement in comprehension skills throughout the class, and students now possess enhanced abilities to interact with diverse texts and derive meaning from them proficiently. All of them expressed how the comp-reading initiative created a big impact in the improvement of their reading comprehension and changed their academic performances. The process of comprehension involves decoding the word of the text and then using basic knowledge to construct of understanding of the message. Comprehension the text means understanding what has been read. Comprehension involves understanding the vocabulary seeing the relationship among words and concepts, organizing idea, recognizing authors' purpose, making judgment, and evaluating (Astri, 2018).

Insights Shared by The School Administrators, Teachers, And Stakeholders with Regards to The Action/Intervention Taken

The major themes and sample statements for research question number 3 were presented in Table 3. Participants had their responses to their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, there are three major themes have emerged: (1) Diverse and Targeted Interventions; (2) Intended Outcomes and Goals; and (3) Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration.

Table 9. *Themes and Sample Statements on The Insights They Share to the School Administrators, Teachers, and Stakeholders with Regards to the Action/Intervention Taken?*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Diverse and Targeted Interventions	Offering one-on-one support sessions for students who needed additional assistance in specific areas of reading comprehension (IDI-10) Introducing explicit instruction on various reading comprehension strategies such as summarization, prediction, and questioning techniques (IDI-12) Providing structured practice activities where students engaged in close reading exercises, annotation tasks, and guided discussions to deepen their understanding of texts (FGD-05) Collaborating with colleagues across disciplines to integrate literacy instruction into content areas and provide interdisciplinary support for reading comprehension skills (FGD-02)
Intended Outcomes and Goals	To enhance our confidence and engagement in reading various types of texts across different subjects (IDI-08) To improve students' overall reading comprehension skills, including their ability to understand main ideas, analyze texts critically, and make inferences (FGD-05) To increase students' confidence and engagement in reading various types of texts across different subjects (FGD- 03) To improve our overall reading comprehension skills, including our ability to understand main ideas, infer meanings, and analyze texts critically (IDI-07)
Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration	Consultation meetings where stakeholders shared their perspectives, concerns, and suggestions regarding the need for interventions to improve reading comprehension (IDI-04) Collaboration sessions where stakeholders worked together to design and implement strategies and interventions tailored to meet the specific needs of students (IDI-06) Regular communication and feedback loops to ensure that stakeholders were informed about the progress and outcomes of the interventions and could provide input for future improvements (FGD-01) Collaborative planning meetings where stakeholders shared input, insights, and concerns regarding the need for interventions to improve reading comprehension (FGD-03)

It was revealed during the conduct of in-depth discussion that the teachers and students mostly mentioned the diverse and targeted interventions. These interventions are based on detailed assessments and are designed to address particular needs, making them more precise and effective compared to general approaches. One of the participants said that collaborating with colleagues across disciplines to integrate literacy instruction into content areas and provide interdisciplinary support for reading comprehension skills. This statement meant somehow way of bringing students to openly engaged in activities of reading. Requirement for sustainability and attaining scale for empirically supported strategies is another thing that is evident from national priorities and reports. It is necessary to have "a national strategy to scale, disseminate, and sustain" diversity-enhancing intervention efforts, but this is easier said than done. Instead, one must attempt to comprehend psychological and social interventions "that mitigate... barriers to workforce diversity" (Valentine & Collins, 2015). The precise results of this study also manifested by the teachers and students that a program or intervention seeks to accomplish are referred to as intended outcomes and goals. As what one of the participants said that promoting a culture of literacy across the school community and foster a lifelong love of reading and learning among students is one of the goals of this study. The results are typically observable and quantifiable, giving a clear sign of accomplishment or advancement. This was supported by Saunders (2020) who claimed that a program or initiative's intended outcomes and goals serve as its road map for success. They guarantee that resources are used effectively, that efforts are concentrated, and that progress is quantifiable.

The teachers and students gathered insights about the stakeholder engagement and collaboration, they stated that regular communication

and feedback loops to ensure that stakeholders were informed about the progress and outcomes of the interventions and could provide input for future improvements, as a result, collaboration and involvement of stakeholders are crucial for tackling difficult problems, encouraging inclusive decision-making, and producing sustainable results, it helps the progress of the students to engage more in activities about reading. Organizations can effect positive change and collective impact in their communities and beyond by proactively involving stakeholders and cultivating collaborative partnerships (Eric, 2018).

Conclusions

Based on the presented results of the study, the researchers conclude that:

Before the implementation of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI), Grade 9 students displayed varying levels of reading comprehension across key areas. Their positive attitudes towards reading ranged from cautious interest to enthusiastic engagement, indicating a readiness for intervention. In terms of main idea identification and question answering, students showed little proficiency in basic comprehension tasks yet demonstrating room for growth in analytical skills. Vocabulary understanding and development varied widely, with some students needing support in acquiring and applying new words effectively. Reading fluency levels also varied, affecting the fluidity and comprehension of their reading experiences. These initial assessments provide a clear baseline from which the CRI can strategically address specific needs and enhance overall reading comprehension among Grade 9 students. By focusing on fostering these factors, the intervention aims to empower students with robust literacy skills essential for academic success and lifelong learning.

After the implementation of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI), Grade 9 students have shown significant improvements in their reading comprehension across multiple dimensions. The initiative has successfully enhanced students' positive attitudes towards reading, fostering increased enthusiasm and engagement with texts. Moreover, students have demonstrated notable progress in identifying main ideas and answering questions, indicating strengthened comprehension skills and analytical abilities. In terms of vocabulary understanding and development, students have expanded their knowledge and usage of words, enabling them to comprehend and articulate concepts more precisely. Additionally, the CRI has contributed to improvements in reading fluency, with students reads smoothly, accurately, and with enhanced expression, which in turn supports deeper comprehension of texts. Overall, the positive outcomes observed post-intervention underscore the effectiveness of the CRI in bolstering Grade 9 students' reading comprehension abilities.

The comparison between pre-test and post-test results following the implementation of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) reveals significant improvements in Grade 9 students' reading comprehension. Statistical analysis indicates a marked difference in several key areas shown with mean scores. Positive attitudes towards reading have notably increased among students, reflecting a greater enjoyment and engagement with reading materials. In terms of main idea identification and question answering, students have shown substantial growth in their ability to comprehend and analyze texts, demonstrating enhanced critical thinking skills. Vocabulary understanding and development have also shown significant progress, with students expanding their lexical knowledge. Moreover, reading fluency has improved significantly post-intervention, as evidenced by smoother and more expressive reading, which correlates with better overall comprehension. These findings reveal the effectiveness of the CRI in elevating Grade 9 students' reading comprehension levels through the interventions. Moving forward, these positive outcomes provide valuable insights for educators and stakeholders, affirming the importance of structured interventions like the CRI in fostering comprehensive literacy skills among students.

Prior to the implementation of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI), Grade 9 students exhibited challenges in various aspects of reading comprehension. Initial assessments revealed concerning levels of positive attitudes towards reading, with many students displaying disinterest or apathy towards engaging with texts. Main idea identification and question answering skills were notably underdeveloped, indicating difficulties in comprehending and analyzing complex texts effectively. Moreover, students demonstrated limited vocabulary understanding and development, struggling with both the acquisition and application of new words in context. This deficiency hindered their ability to grasp nuanced meanings and articulate ideas clearly. Additionally, reading fluency presented as a significant barrier, with students often reading hesitantly and with limited expression, impacting their overall comprehension and engagement with texts. These baseline findings underscore the critical need for targeted interventions like the CRI to address the fundamental gaps in Grade 9 students' reading comprehension abilities.

After the implementation of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI), Grade 9 students have shown significant development in their reading comprehension abilities across various dimensions. The intervention has led to noticeable improvements in several key areas. Students have displayed increased enthusiasm and engagement with reading materials, showing eagerness to explore different texts, and developing a stronger appreciation for reading in both academic and personal contexts. They have made substantial progress in identifying main ideas and answering questions, demonstrating improved comprehension skills. Additionally, students have expanded their vocabulary knowledge, using a wider range of words in context and enhancing their ability to comprehend texts thoroughly and express ideas precisely. Moreover, reading fluency has significantly improved, with students reading more smoothly, accurately, and expressively, contributing to enhanced overall comprehension and enjoyment of reading materials. These illustrates the effectiveness of the CRI in developing Grade 9 students' reading comprehension levels.

The results of the Comp-Reading Initiative (CRI) highlight valuable insights for school administrators, teachers, and stakeholders regarding the effectiveness of targeted interventions in enhancing Grade 9 students' reading comprehension. The initiative has

demonstrated that structured approaches focusing on positive attitudes towards reading, main idea identification and critical analysis skills, vocabulary understanding and development, and reading fluency can significantly improve students' overall literacy proficiency. Fostering an environment where students are encouraged to engage actively with diverse reading materials leads to heightened enthusiasm and deeper comprehension. Moving forward, administrators can prioritize ongoing professional development for teachers to refine instructional strategies that promote these critical skills. Collaborative efforts among educators and stakeholders can ensure sustained support and reinforcement of literacy initiatives, ultimately fostering a culture of academic excellence and lifelong learning within the school community.

The researcher of this study suggests the following recommendations in the light of the aforementioned information and findings.

First and foremost, Department of Education (DepEd), they have the power to help the students in their studies by proposing studied similar to this endeavor through the teachers of different schools to foster high level of reading comprehension among the students not only in Grade 9 which this study put focus. Also, they might consider proposing more seminars, and trainings that will help the teachers to be fully equipped and knowledgeable in integrating various ways and constructed educational tasks.

Secondly, teachers, they should incorporate learning activities that meets diverse needs of the students at all levels, which is necessary for an interactive learning experience of the students and enrich not only their reading comprehension but also other aspects. In order to accommodate the student's varied learning needs, abilities, and preferences, they should also tailor differentiated activities and instructions, which includes teaching methods, materials, and assessments.

As for the students, they are recommended to explore more about the concepts not only focusing on the development and enhancement of their reading comprehension but also the other areas which may help them succeed not only in academic aspect but also in real-life circumstances. Practice and explore different ways to hone one's abilities and skills to lessen academic barriers and increase productivity.

For the future researchers, it is strongly advised to include a control group in subsequent studies which this study did not include. By incorporating a control group that does not receive the intervention, researchers can more effectively isolate and evaluate the specific effects of the intervention itself. This comparative approach not only strengthens the internal validity of the study but also provides clearer insights into whether observed changes can be attributed to the intervention or other external factors.

Furthermore, employing Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for comparative analysis of post-test results between the intervention and control groups is also recommended. ANCOVA is particularly valuable as it allows researchers to statistically adjust for baseline differences or covariates that may influence outcomes. This adjustment enhances the accuracy of determining the true impact of the intervention, thereby yielding more reliable findings and reducing potential biases.

Lastly, it is essential for future researchers to transparently acknowledge and discuss the limitations identified in this study. These limitations include factors such as sample size constraints, methodological weaknesses, or specific contextual variables that could impact the interpretation of results. Addressing these limitations not only demonstrates scholarly rigor but also guides subsequent investigations by highlighting areas for improvement or further exploration.

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